

Model representations and sample size for a two arm pre-post study with a metric outcome

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Study design

In the hypothetical SAFE study, a metric outcome (the O-PACIC score) is collected at baseline (*pre*) and again after six months (*post*) and compared between treatment and control arm (*group*).

Models

Comparing score changes ($post_i - pre_i$) between groups suffers from the phenomenon “regression to the mean”, meaning that differences with low/high (i.e. below/above average) baselines tend to be larger/smaller than the effect of the treatment.

Randomization might level out these effects but (a) randomization might fail and (b) even if it doesn't, mere score changes still don't capture the full information about the treatment effect: A score increase from a low baseline is weaker evidence for an effective treatment than the same increase starting from a high baseline. Ignoring this information results in loss of power and a higher sample size (see last section). Therefore, the baseline variable *pre* should be taken into consideration (i.e. “adjusted for”).

Since baseline values must be considered anyway, the analysis can be simplified by comparing *post* values instead of the differences $post_i - pre_i$. So, in a nutshell, the analysis compares the values of *post* between the two *groups*, additionally taking the baseline variable *pre* into account.

The comparison of *post* between the two *groups* is basically an unpaired

two sample *t*-test (1)

(which is equivalent to a one-way ANOVA with two *groups*) but the additional metric variable *pre* turns that into an ANCOVA problem. The ANCOVA model maps the two explanatory variables *pre* and *group* to the dependent variable *post*. This can be written in terms of a linear regression model as follows:

$$post_i \approx a + b \cdot pre_i + c \cdot group_i \quad (2)$$


```
##           Estimate    Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) 1.3260286 0.0078809242
## pre         0.7016890 0.0001827368
## group1      0.6049043 0.0125845152
```

Note that setting $b = 0$ in model (2) would correspond to a two sample t -test/ANOVA of $post$ values, and $b = 1$ to comparing the changes $post_i - pre_i$ between $groups$. In ANCOVA, b gets estimated! However, it's the treatment effect c that we are primarily interested in.

Now, pre_i and $post_i$ are measurements of the same $score$ variable but at different times. Therefore, they can be recoded to $score$ and a new variable $time$, as the following tables show:

id	group	pre	post
1	0	1.5	2.2
2	1	1.6	4.2
3	0	1.7	1.8

id	group	time	score
1	0	pre	1.5
1	0	post	2.2
2	1	pre	1.6
2	1	post	4.2
3	0	pre	1.7
3	0	post	1.8

pre and $post$ in a wide table vs. $time$ and $score$ in a long table

However, the effect of the variable $group$ can not be fully assessed if at time $t = 0$ there is only one $group$ (just the controls if nobody has received the treatment yet). Assuming this, the long table should actually be

id	group	time	score
1	0	pre	1.5
1	0	post	2.2
2	0	pre	1.6
2	1	post	4.2
3	0	pre	1.7
3	0	post	1.8

note $group = 0$ in row two

and only the interaction $group \cdot time$ can be estimated. The following repeated measures model is then an (approximately) equivalent alternative to the ANCOVA model (2) above (ref. 3, p. 904 and appendix A):

$$score_{it} \approx a' + b' \cdot time_{it} + c' \cdot group_i \cdot time_{it} \quad (3)$$


```
##           Estimate      Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) 2.8125000 3.437029e-37
## time         0.4469055 5.285855e-03
## time:group1 0.6819415 9.730357e-04
```

Again, it's the coefficient c' — the effect of the treatment ($group = 1$) after six months ($time = post$) — that we are interested in.

Sample size

The sample size required for the SAFE study can be calculated using

$$n = n_{\text{two sample } t\text{-test}} \cdot (1 - r^2) \quad (4)$$

where r is the correlation coefficient between pre and $post$.

In order to intuitively understand this, remember that (2) and (3) are essentially “adjusted t -tests” (1) that take into account how much the baselines influence the $post$ scores. This influence is captured by the correlation r . The more similar pre and $post$ are, the less individuals are needed for the test because similarity reduces variation (the denominator of the t -test statistic). Consider the extremes:

- If $r = 0$ (pre and $post$ uncorrelated) then pre doesn't exert any influence on $post$ at all and therefore needn't be taken into consideration. The sample size is just the sample size of a normal t -test with two independent samples:

$$n = n_{\text{two sample } t\text{-test}} \cdot (1 - 0^2) = n_{\text{two sample } t\text{-test}} \cdot 1 = n_{\text{two sample } t\text{-test}}$$

- If $|r| = 1$ (perfectly correlated pre and $post$) then pre yields perfect information about $post$, and there is no need to perform any test at all. The sample size is 0:

$$n = n_{\text{two sample } t\text{-test}} \cdot (1 - 1^2) = n_{\text{two sample } t\text{-test}} \cdot 0 = 0$$

Note that while the factor $n_{\text{two sample } t\text{-test}}$ in (4) behaves in a “natural” way (the stronger the treatment the smaller the sample size), the factor $(1 - r^2)$ on the right hand side *increases* with more effective treatments because effective treatments add additional variability and therefore *reduce* the correlation. This might not be intuitive!

Further note that the corresponding sample size formula for comparing the changes $post_i - pre_i$ between *groups* would replace $(1 - r^2)$ by $2(1 - r)$ (assuming the same pre mean in both groups). For a typical $r = 0.5$ this implies that ANCOVA (2) and the repeated measures model (3) require $1 - (1 - 0.5^2)/(2 - 2 \cdot 0.5) = 1 - 0.75/1 = 25\%$ less observations than a t -test with the *score* changes (or the $post$ scores, for that matter).

Finally, if perceived as a clustered trial, the required sample size for the SAFE study has to be inflated by an additional design effect factor $d = 1 + (n_c - 1) \cdot \rho$, as usual with clustered designs (n_c = number of individuals per cluster, ρ = intracluster correlation coefficient (ICC)), and r is then the correlation between pre and $post$ cluster means.

References

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